

**NANOSTRUCTURES AND
DYNAMICS *of*
BLOCK COPOLYMER SYSTEMS
by CELL DYNAMICS SIMULATION
and APPLICATION *for*
SUPERCOMPUTER SYSTEMS**

LUDWIG SCHREIER

Update 2023

It's well over a decade since this thesis has been written. Since then, several events took place. Firstly, the research group of Prof. Andrei V. Zvelindovsky moved to the University of Lincoln, UK. The former Soft Matter Group successfully evolved into the Centre for Computational Physics. [1] Additionally, the Fachhochschule Wiesbaden evolved into Hochschule RheinMain, with its physics department still rocking. Secondly, the author of the thesis perused his out-of-academic career path. Thirdly, the company Nvidia turned into a superpower of computation with high-end devices. Its business went multi-fold in the financials, currently standing at about \$ 650 B market cap. [2] Since 2009, nearly all computational- and data-heavy models across all sciences adapted GPU-powered devices for some number crunching. The next door has already opened by adding AI-optimized capabilities. The physics of the 'cell dynamics simulation' was put forward by AVZ and colleagues. [3,4] As proposed in this thesis, a Crank-Nicolson solver was later studied. [5] Meanwhile, the authors' interest into physics continues. The key element of the thesis, besides the computational study of polymers, is the functional. [6–8] This fundamental "item" in physics and mathematical "space" connects to variational methods, to quantum physics, superconductors, and many other important areas. [9,10] The simple model, which was studied in this thesis, can then be considered a "swiss tool" in theoretical physics and is widely used by other models and branches. [11] Finally, (computational) Soft matter physics continues to be a field of active research. This is an invitation! [9,12,13]

- [1] Centre for Computational Physics, <https://comp-physics-lincoln.org/>.
- [2] NVIDIA Corporation (NVDA) Stock Price, News, Quote & History - Yahoo Finance, <https://finance.yahoo.com/quote/NVDA/>.
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NANOSTRUCTURES AND DYNAMICS OF BLOCK COPOLYMER
SYSTEMS BY CELL DYNAMICS SIMULATION AND APPLICATION
FOR SUPERCOMPUTER SYSTEMS

BY

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June 2009, Preston, UK

There is nothing as practical as a good theory.

Kurt Lewin

An algorithm must be seen to be believed.

Donald Knuth

This thesis results from work carried out at the University of Central Lancashire, within the Computational Physics Group of Dr. A. V. Zvelindovsky in the period of March 2009 to June 2009. The work was performed under the supervision of:

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- ASTS seminars, Cell Dynamics - Integrating a new Mesoscale code with MaterialsScript, Accelrys Ltd., Cambridge, United Kingdom, February 2009
- A. V. Zvelindovsky and L. Schreier, Soft nano-structures from block copolymers: Cell Dynamics Simulation, Accelrys Science Forum 2009, Cambridge, United Kingdom, May 2009
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Publications

Recent publications related to the field of study:

- G. J. A. Sevink, M. Pinna, L. Schreier, A. V. Zvelindovsky, On the Melting Mechanism of Electric-Field-Induced Alignment of Block Copolymer Lamellae (*In preparation*)
- L. Schreier, Cell Dynamics - Integrating a new Mesoscale code with *MaterialsScript*, Internal report, Accelrys Ltd., Cambridge, UK, 2009
- M. Pinna, L. Schreier, A. V. Zvelindovsky, Mechanisms of electric-field-induced alignment of block copolymer lamellae, *Soft Matter* **5** 970-973, 2009

Abstract:

We demonstrate that two mechanisms of lamellae reorientation observed experimentally under applied electric field [A. Böker H. Elbs, H. Hänsel, A. Knoll, S. Ludwigs, H. Zettl, V. Urban, V. Abetz, A. H. E. Müller and G. Krausch, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 2002, 89, 135502] which have been previously described within dynamic self consistent field theory [A. V. Zvelindovsky and G. J. A. Sevink, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 2003, 90, 049601] can be fully explained within a much more simple model using the Ginzburg-Landau Hamiltonian. A third alignment mechanism has been identified which was not previously reported. A more complete picture of reorientation under electric field emerges that clarifies the crucial role of structural defects.

- Schreier *et al.* American Physical Society (APS) March meeting 2009, Pittsburgh, USA. Poster session: Coarse Grained Simulation of Block Copolymer Systems

Abstract:

We present results of coarse-grained computer modelling of block copolymer systems based on Cell Dynamics Simulation. Phase transitions induced by external factors in various block copolymer systems are investigated. This contribution puts focus on dynamics of systems subjected to two examples of external fields such as an applied electric field and confinements.

Reoccurring notations and symbols

Symbol	Description
∂	Partial differential operator
Δ	Laplace operator, differential operator ($\Delta = \nabla^2$)
ψ	Order parameter
M	Mobility parameter
\mathcal{F}	Free energy functional
D	Diffusion coefficient
B	Chain connectivity parameter
\mathbf{j}	Flux
μ	Chemical potential
\mathcal{H}	Hamiltonian
τ	Temperature parameter
A	phenomenological parameter
ν	phenomenological parameter
u	phenomenological parameter
f	Volume fraction
\mathbf{r}	Spatial vector for N dimensions
$\langle\langle * \rangle\rangle - *$	Numerical Laplacian notation
$G(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}')$	Green function
$g(\psi)$	Map function
$\phi_{A, B}$	Volume notation for diblock copolymer
$N_{A, B}$	Degree of polymerisation
L	Box size, spatial box
t	Time
χ	Flory-Huggins parameter
T	Temperature
k_B	Boltzmann constant
ξ	Noise term
η	Noise amplitude

C_1, C_2	Constants
b	Segment length
s	Empirical function
\mathcal{F}_S	Short range free energy
\mathcal{F}_L	Long range free energy
T_{CPU}, T_{GPU}	GPU, CPU time
δ	Delta function
x	space coordinate
\mathcal{S}	Stencil
h	Grid size
α, β, γ	Weighting factors
$S_{\mathbf{k}}$	Structure factor
I	Intensity
q, k	Wave vectors
NN	Nearest neighbours
NNN	Next-nearest neighbours
m, n	Constants
\mathcal{F}^{FFT}	Fast Fourier Transform

Table 0.1: Reoccurring notations and symbols

1 AIM OF THE THESIS

Modern day technology requires miniaturisation on the nano-scale. One of the directions to achieve this lays within Soft Condensed Matter Physics, which includes such phenomena as self-organisation and self-assembly of materials. One of most promising materials-candidates to design nano-structures are block copolymers, block-chains of chemically bonded different polymer-blocks[6]. These materials are intrinsically very complex, and in most cases their behaviour cannot be understood without computer simulations.

In **Section 1**, the basic concepts of block copolymer physics and the specific theoretical model called Cell Dynamics simulation are reviewed as an introduction. Modelling of block copolymers introduces a new way to improve research in nanotechnology. Many key-technologies like semiconductor lithography have reached a stage at which the relevant processes can be simulated directly and lead to new insights and development or optimisation of novel applications. Latest research using block copolymers in nanoscale technologies includes nanolithography[7, 8], advanced information storage technology[9], photonic crystals[10, 11], biochemical engineering, biomedicine, drug delivery, microelectronics, etc.[6]. There is a clear need for fast and reliable computational methods. Using computer simulation to study nature, one can validate the underlying theoretical models and compare with experimental results. The aim in this section is to introduce the reader into the field of Soft Matter and block copolymer physics.

In **Section 2**, Cell Dynamics scheme was implemented on GPU-based supercomputers. Computer simulations are required as a necessary part of computer-aided design of new nano-materials. In order to be relevant for experiments and subsequently for the industrial processes, computer simulations should address time scales and simulation sample sizes of real experimental systems. Most of molecular simulation methods are still far from that goal, and therefore, are of only academic interest. In contrast, the coarse-grained simulation methods, such as Cell Dynamics simulation, have approached that border line. However, even for these methods a standard PC does not provide a simulation speed which is desired for a computer-aided design. The only solution, which existed till now is to use multiprocessor supercomputers and supercomputer clusters. This is a very expensive solution (requiring also a dedicated staff to maintain supercomputers and clusters), which is out of reach for a typical experimental or industrial laboratory, where materials design is done. A very new technology that uses the graphics card (or graphics processing unit, GPU) of a PC instead of the conventional processor (central processing unit,

CPU) for numerical computations, emerged. Due to the GPU internal architecture, it allows for parallel processing of numerical tasks. This new technology offers a supercomputer at the office desk. However, all numerical schemes and computer codes developed till now for conventional CPUs cannot be directly transported to GPU and do require a separate coding from the beginning in a specialised parallel computer programming language. The aim in this section is to write the Cell Dynamics scheme for GPU supercomputer systems.

In **Section 3**, several different Laplacian operators were implemented to study the isotropicity for lamellae systems and analyze the influence of structure formation.

The Cell Dynamics scheme requires numerical solution of differential equations on a computational grid. The crucial part of this is discretization of the differential operators, of which the Laplacian is the most important one in the formulation of the Cell Dynamics simulation. There are infinitely many ways to discretize differential operators. In 80s, when the original Cell Dynamics scheme was proposed, a particular discretization of the Laplacian was employed, which provided the fastest speed keeping and a correctness of the discretization (more precisely, one of its properties - isotropicity of the Laplacian results) on a reasonable level. Since then two factors have been changed: the speed of computers increased drastically and the perspective of the direct technological application of Cell Dynamics method requires now as precise calculation as possible within the limitations of the method. However, the balance of speed and isotropicity of the Cell Dynamics discretization was not studied. In this section, the aim was to study the isotropicity of Cell Dynamics scheme for different Laplacian operators.

In **Section 4**, Cell Dynamics scheme is computationally very fast. However, for different system parameters the scheme is unstable. The diffusive dynamics that the scheme is based on allow in general to use other solver methods like Crank-Nicholson that are known to be more stable. The approach for implementation is given herein. In the last section, the aim was to conduct research on Cell Dynamics scheme using Crank-Nicholson method.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 Physics and chemistry of block copolymers

Copolymers are molecules formed of several types of monomers (repeating polymer units) connected in a polymer chain. Arranging monomers into distinct blocks, various block copolymers (BCP) are formed as can be seen in Figure 2.1.

In Figure 2.2 AB diblock copolymer is shown, to illustrate a structure of the complete macromolecule. Staudinger and Fritschy first proposed in 1922 that giant molecules called Macromolecules exist[12]. Every block type, either A or B can consist of different monomers, for example styrene, butadiene or isoprene. This particular examples are thermoplastic elastomers because they do not require vulcanisation[12]. There exist linear, cyclic, branched, alternating, periodic and other architectures, see Figure 2.1. More complex configurations such as ABC or $ABCBA$, ABC star or ABC hetero-arm can be found[13]. Moreover, random and graft copolymers exist[14]. The reachness of the structure has almost no limit[13]. The composition of the AB diblock copolymer is given by the volume-fraction $f = N_A/N$, where N_A is number of A monomers. The degree of polymerisation N is the number of monomers in the chain, $N = N_A + N_B$. Because the chain lengths of monomers vary statistically, it is an average quantity. A value of a molecular mass of 10000 g/mol can be considered as a lower limit when speaking of macromolecules. Molecules can be cross-linked to form gels or, in the case of high linkage density, an elastomer (rubber).

Figure 2.1: Examples of BCP. Different colours represent different blocks. a) AB diblock copolymer, b) ABA triblock copolymer, c) grafted AB copolymer, d) star ABC triblock, e) linear ABC triblock.

Figure 2.2: PS-*b*-PBD diblock with mesoscale bead representation for Dissipative Particle Dynamics (DPD) as drawn with Materials Studio[2]

Methods for the experimental analysis of block copolymers include Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM), Small Angle Neutron Scattering (SANS), Small Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS)[15], Evanescent wave light scattering, Light Scattering, X-ray Photon Correlation Spectroscopy (XPCS). Moreover, Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) can be used to study segmental motions in block copolymer solutions[14, 15].

Theoretical studies include analytic theories and computer simulations. For the analysis of computational results, methods like Fourier Transformation [as Fast Fourier Transformation (FFT) or Discrete Fourier Transformation (DFT)] and advanced 2D or 3D visualisation techniques are important. Beyond visualization, Minkowski functionals [or Morphological Image Analysis, (MIA)] are an efficient tool for image analysis[16, 17, 18, 19]. Minkowski functionals can be used to study the phase transition and kinetics of block copolymers in greater detail and reveal important morphological information[1]. It is possible to calculate four Minkowski functionals for the three-dimensional discretized object[1]. In comparison with Fourier-analysis, Minkowski functionals provide more detail for aperiodic structures, which are often found at the initial stages of microphase separation where the structure is highly defected[16]. A detailed discussion why pattern analysis is so important is given by Sevink[16].

The domain size of copolymers is of particular interest for research, engineering of novel technologies and therefore of commercial interest. The symmetry of morphologies as well as size of the micro domains can be controlled by varying the molecular weight, composition, concentration and temperature[20]. The interested reader is referred to the review by Bates and Fredrickson about block copolymers as designer soft materials[13].

2.2 Block copolymer microphase separation

Copolymer systems exhibit a very interesting phenomena of microphase separation or order-disorder transition (ODT), to form nanostructures with a typical domain size of the order of 5 – 100 nm, depending on the block length[21]. The influence of the temperature T on the system causes formation of ordered morphologies on the nanoscale, resulting in periodic nano-structures similar to crystals[1, 22, 23, 10]. Typically, an isotropic grain structure is obtained which is a random distribution of microdomain orientations[24].

The physical reason for ordering is microphase separation, with short-range repulsive interaction between different blocks. Block copolymers consist of at least two immiscible covalently bonded monomers. The blocks cannot separate totally in space (macrophase separation) due to their chemical (covalent) bonding. For diblock copolymer systems, different equilibrium morphologies are found for different volume fraction, f as it is shown in Figure 2.5. A lamellae (LAM) configuration results from a symmetric diblock copolymer, see Figure 2.5. Changes to the volume fraction f leads to more asymmetric morphologies, e.g. the bicontinuous cubic gyroid phase (GYR)[1, 22] with $I\bar{a}3d$ symmetry. Other morphologies include body centered cubic spheres (BCC) (see Figure 2.5) and hexagonally ordered cylinders (HEX).

The interaction between blocks is often described by the *Flory-Huggins* parameter, χ , which is inversely

Figure 2.3: Phase diagram from Self-Consistent Field Theory (SCFT) calculations that shows regions of different phases for AB diblock copolymers with $\chi N > 10.5$: S, spheres (BCC); C, cylinder (CYL); G, gyroid (GYR); L, lamellae (LAM); S_{cp} , spheres on edge[3].

Figure 2.4: Experimental phase diagram for AB diblock copolymer with indication of different phases that can be related to theoretical calculations[4].

proportional to the temperature. This parameter together with the volume-fraction f are the two most important parameters controlling block copolymer nanostructures. The phase diagram in Figures 2.3 and 2.4 from Matsen and Schick was calculated for AB diblock copolymer and compares well to experimental diagram from Khandpur[4, 3]. Figure 2.3 shows for different values of the volume fraction f and χN different resulting phases as can be depicted from Figure 2.5. For values of $\chi N < 10.5$, only a disordered melt is predicted, however above the order-disorder transition, five microphase structures occur within regions of thermodynamic stability as is shown in Figure 2.5.

Figure 2.5: Equilibrium AB diblock copolymer morphologies as function of the volume fraction, f .

2.3 Cell Dynamics simulation for diblock copolymer systems

Mesoscale modelling is a fairly new and active direction of computational materials science which studies phenomena within the scales of $(10 - 1000) \text{ nm}$ and $(10^{-8} - 1)$ seconds[25]. It aims to bridge the gap between atomistic simulations and continuum calculations in order to form a multiscale simulation ladder, see Figure 2.6. Fast degrees of freedom in a system are averaged out, making it possible to model longer time and length scales[16]. Nanoparticles, liquid-crystalline structures, crystals, polymers (in particular complex polymer systems like block copolymers) and other soft materials are the object of mesoscale modelling. These studies are regarded critical in developing superior materials for the future. In order to predict macromolecular properties (e.g. bulk structure, rheological and mechanical properties), a deep understand of the underlying physical mechanisms is needed. To describe mesoscale problems, today's most common multiscale methods include coarse-graining strategies, which enable seamless *in silicio* multiscale modelling and simulation workflows[26]. Taking calculation results from quantum or atomistic simulation into account, it is possible to propose a coarse-grained description for a *bead* in a mesoscale simulation as can be see in Figure 2.2. Electronic structure calculations can

Figure 2.6: Length and time scales for different modelling approaches: Quantum mechanics (QM), Molecular regime Molecular Mechanics (MM) or Molecular Dynamics (MD), Mesoscale modelling by Cell Dynamics (CDS) or Dissipative Particle Dynamics (DPD) and Continuum regime (Finite-Element-Method, FEM)

be used to derive a force field. Molecular Dynamics can be applied, using the force field to refine a coarse-grained description. Morphology can be simulated and studied by mesoscale simulation using the coarse-grained description and finally feed it into macroscopic methods (e.g. finite element methods, computational fluid-dynamics) for transport or mechanical properties by solving continuum equations (see also Ref. [26, 27] for an excellent review in coarse-graining methods). Computational methods to study mesoscale phenomena include Molecular Dynamics (MD), Monte Carlo (MC), Dissipative Particle Dynamics (DPD), Self-Consistent Field Theory (SCFT), Dynamic Density Functional Theory (DDFT)[25, 17], field theoretic simulation[28] and Cell Dynamics simulation (CDS)[29]. These methods offer a possibility of virtual experimentation. Consider a typical laboratory setup, which includes the synthesis of polymers, the measurements of properties and study of morphology. Here, computational methods offer a simpler option to build molecules and calculate properties for an almost unlimited amount of samples.

Cell Dynamics simulation which is based Ginzburg-Landau Hamiltonian, is a fast computational method to describe phase separation phenomena, alignment and kinetics of copolymers[30, 29, 21, 31, 1]. Cell Dynamics technique can be reduced to a Chan-Hilliard (CH) equation. The Chan-Hilliard equation was originally proposed by Cahn and Hilliard as a fourth-order parabolic partial differential equation describ-

ing the phenomenon of metal alloy spinodal decomposition[32]. Favvas and Mitropoulos give a brief review about spinodal decomposition, that is phase separation to occur spontaneously without the presence of a nucleation step[33]. Cell Dynamics was introduced by Oono and Puri to describe microphase separation phenomena by computationally efficient means without considering the conventional analytical formulation in terms of partial differential equations[29, 31, 30]. Cell Dynamics simulation can study polymer mixtures (blends, alloys and composites). Recently, Cell Dynamics has been used to study diblock copolymer nanostructures, with extension for shear alignment[1], electrical field alignment[23], curvatures[34], nano-particle inclusions, etc.

The method introduces an order parameter ψ , which represents the local density difference of the constituent monomers and is related to each cell of the spatial lattice[10, 1]:

$$\psi = \phi_A - \phi_B + (1 - 2f) \quad (2.1)$$

The fundamental partial differential equation of interest is given by:

$$\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = M \nabla^2 \frac{\delta \mathcal{F}(\psi)}{\delta \psi} + \eta \xi \quad (2.2)$$

where η is the amplitude of the noise, ξ is a random Gaussian noise and M , a phenomenal mobility constant that sets the timescale for the diffusive process (dimensionless time is tM/a_0^2)[1, 23, 29]. The free energy functional \mathcal{F} , in equation (2.2) is related to the chemical potential μ [21]:

$$\mu = \frac{\delta \mathcal{F}(\psi)}{\delta \psi} \quad (2.3)$$

The flux due to the chemical potential is expressed as[21]:

$$\mathbf{j} = -M \nabla \mu \quad (2.4)$$

The scheme must satisfy the continuity equation,

$$\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{j} \quad (2.5)$$

which results in equation (2.2). The model described includes a conserved order parameter, that implies

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int d\mathbf{r} \psi = 0 \quad (2.6)$$

which restricts the noise term in equation (2.2). The total free energy $\mathcal{F}(\psi)$ can be divided into the short range part \mathcal{F}_S and the long range part \mathcal{F}_L [35, 30, 36]. \mathcal{F}_S is:

$$\mathcal{F}_S = \int d\mathbf{r} \left(\mathcal{H}(\psi) + \frac{D}{2} |\nabla \psi|^2 \right) \quad (2.7)$$

where $\mathcal{H}(\psi)$ is the Hamiltonian. The gradient term in equation (2.7) limits spatial inhomogeneities[37]. The Hamiltonian $\mathcal{H}(\psi)$ has the form[21]:

$$\mathcal{H}(\psi) = \left(-\frac{\tau}{2} + \frac{A}{2}(1-2f)^2 \right) \psi^2 + \frac{\nu}{3}(1-2f)\psi^3 + \frac{u}{4}\psi^4 \quad (2.8)$$

The cubic term which is non-zero at $f \neq 1/2$ is required to account for the full range of non-lamellar phases[21]. In equations (2.8), τ is a temperature parameter and measures the depth of the quench[29] and is proportional to a reduced temperature[37]. The parameters A , D , ν and u are phenomenological parameters (u and ν do not allow for a compact representation, but they can be computed by evaluating the appropriate vertex functions given by Leibler[38]). In Cell Dynamics simulation the values of these parameters, which are used for different morphologies can be found in the literature[1, 21, 39]. Moreover they are not specifically limited to diblock copolymers. Next, a long-range term, \mathcal{F}_L results from chain connectivity (or conformational entropy of the block copolymer chain [35]) and is written as[21]:

$$\mathcal{F}_L = \frac{B}{2} \int d\mathbf{r} \int d\mathbf{r}' G(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}') \psi(\mathbf{r}) \psi(\mathbf{r}') \quad (2.9)$$

where $G(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}')$ is Green's function for the Laplace operator, $\nabla^2 G(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}') = -\delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}')$ [35, 21, 1]. Summation of \mathcal{F}_S and \mathcal{F}_L gives the total free energy, \mathcal{F} :

$$\mathcal{F}(\psi) = \int d\mathbf{r} \left(\mathcal{H}(\psi) + \frac{D}{2} |\nabla \psi|^2 \right) + \frac{B}{2} \int d\mathbf{r} \int d\mathbf{r}' G(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}') \psi(\mathbf{r}) \psi(\mathbf{r}') \quad (2.10)$$

All parameters can be related to molecular characteristics. In principle, it can be done by deriving coarse-grained models from lower-level (atomistic) models or from the experimental results. For instance, according to Ohta and Kawasaki[40],

$$\tau' = -\frac{1}{2N} \left(\chi N - \frac{s(f)}{4f^2(1-f)^2} \right), \quad D = \frac{b^2}{48f(1-f)}, \quad B = \frac{9}{4N^2 b^2 f^2 (1-f)^2} \quad (2.11)$$

where $\tau' = -\tau + A(1-2f)^2$, χ is the *Flory-Huggins* parameter, $s(f)$ is an empirical fitting function of the order of 1, e.g. $s(0.5) = 0.9$, $s(0.3) = 1.0$, and b is the segment length[40]. The parameters u and ν are very complex functions which can be only approximately replaced by constants. The *Flory-Huggins* parameter is inversely proportional to the temperature:

$$\chi \propto \frac{C_1}{T} + C_2 \quad (2.12)$$

and is a enthalpic interaction parameter between the two polymer blocks[21]. The product of χ and N describes the degree of immiscibility. Given a symmetric diblock copolymer with volume-fraction $f = 1/2$, a mean-field theory predicts that at order-disorder-transition, $\chi N = 10.5$. For $\chi N < 10.5$,

Figure 2.7: Zoom of different length scales for AB type diblock copolymer lamellae simulation results by Cell Dynamics. The method describes phenomenological block copolymer phase separation at the nano-scale.

diblock copolymers are in disordered phase, see Figure (2.3)[21]. With decreasing temperature and hence increasing χN , the extent between the blocks increase[21]. In simulation the dimensionless parameters $\tilde{D} = D/a_0^2$ and $\tilde{B} = B/a_0^2$ are used. For simplicity the notations D and B are used instead of \tilde{D} and \tilde{B} . Parameter a_0 is the lattice cell size and set to 1. Different morphologies [lamellae (LAM), spherical (SPH), cylindrical (CYL), gyroid (GYR)] can be obtained by varying two main controlling parameters, molecular composition f and the temperature like-parameter, τ' [1].

The numerical time-evolution of equation (2.2) by means of Cell Dynamics simulation is given by[29, 31, 30, 41, 32, 39, 1, 21]:

$$\psi_{\mathbf{r}}^{t+1} = g(\psi_{\mathbf{r}}^t) + D[\langle\langle\psi_{\mathbf{r}}^t\rangle\rangle - \psi_{\mathbf{r}}^t] - \langle\langle g(\psi_{\mathbf{r}}^t) + D[\langle\langle\psi_{\mathbf{r}}^t\rangle\rangle - \psi_{\mathbf{r}}^t] - \psi_{\mathbf{r}}^t \rangle\rangle - B\psi_{\mathbf{r}}^t + \eta\xi_{\mathbf{r}}^t \quad (2.13)$$

where \mathbf{r} denotes the lattice site $\mathbf{r} = (i, j, k)$ for three dimensions. In equation (2.13), $\eta\xi_{\mathbf{r}}^t$ is a noise term with η being the noise amplitude, ξ a Gaussian random noise and $\langle\langle\psi\rangle\rangle - \psi$, is a discrete Laplacian. For three dimensions, one can use[29, 32, 21, 1],

$$\langle\langle\psi\rangle\rangle = \frac{6}{80} \sum_{NN} \psi + \frac{3}{80} \sum_{NNN} \psi + \frac{1}{80} \sum_{NNNN} \psi \quad (2.14)$$

In two dimensions, the discrete Laplacian takes the form[29, 32]:

$$\langle\langle\psi\rangle\rangle = \frac{1}{6} \sum_{NN} \psi + \frac{1}{12} \sum_{NNN} \psi \quad (2.15)$$

Here N stands for the lattice sites, i.e. NN addresses the nearest neighbours, NNN - the next-nearest neighbours and so forth. In equation (2.13), the term, $g(\psi)$ is related to equation (2.8) and referred as *map* function which can be precalculated:

$$g(\psi) = (1 + \tau - A(1 - 2f)^2)\psi - v(1 - 2f)\psi^2 - w\psi^3 \quad (2.16)$$

The Cell Dynamics scheme starts with assigning random numbers (in range $\{0 \dots 1\}$, e.g. -0.5 to 0.5) to the order parameter array at time step 0. The evaluation of equation (2.14) together with application of periodic boundary conditions for a square grid[42, 43, 44] lead to the time evolution of $\psi_{\mathbf{r}}^{t+1}$ according to equation (2.13) for different time steps, until equilibrium of structure is found. A typical Cell Dynamics simulation run (at a distinct time step) in two dimensions is shown in Figure 2.7.

2.4 Summary of tasks

The following tasks were performed:

- The concepts of physics of microphase separation, which leads to complex block copolymer structures were studied.
- The theoretical and experimental techniques used to study these structures were reviewed.
- The theoretical model Cell Dynamics was learnt and in particular:
 - How the evolution of block copolymer structures can be described in terms of the order parameter.
 - How the Ginzburg-Landau Hamiltonian from the general theory of phase transition can be applied to describe block copolymer structures.
 - How the differential equation of Ginzburg-Landau dynamics can be numerically discretized in a particular form of Cell Dynamics simulation.

3 IMPLEMENTATION OF CELL DYNAMICS SIMULATION FOR GPU-BASED SUPERCOMPUTERS

Abstract

The supercomputer system used was a multiprocessor graphics processing unit (GPU) that was addressed using the NVIDIA CUDA programming environment, that is a very new computing technology from NVIDIA company which attracts considerable interest in modern computational physics and high performance computing (HPC).

Three new codes have been developed: C version of Cell Dynamics simulation employing two-dimension to one-dimension domain decomposition and GPU versions of Cell Dynamics scheme with two different internal implementation strategies. For two-dimensional lamellae block copolymer systems, the codes have been benchmarked against each other as well as against a existing Fortran 90 reference version. Performance of the codes as a whole as well as of various internal parts has been analysed in detail. For a lamellae system of 1024^2 grid points, 70 fold speedup of GPU code was achieved compared to Fortran 90 code. The results allowed for proposing a new efficient way of the GPU code speedup. It was also found that the two-dimension to one-dimension decomposition allows the C version to make use of the single-instruction-multiple-data (SIMD) architecture of the CPU. Therefore the internal architecture of the C code becomes similar to calculation pathways of GPU code. As result, that brings the performance close to GPU version of Cell Dynamics.

3.1 Introduction

Supercomputing is a highly competitive area and today's cutting edge of scientific research. In the last decades, the field of computational science has undergone many different changes in hardware as well as software methodology to compute phenomena's that are not accessible without heavy resources to humans anymore.

For newly build systems, operation costs, ease of usage, scalability and professional support can be considered as most important factors for deployment. New hybrid designs are famous, for example the mixing of different processors and latest system infrastructure hardware. Programming for supercomputers involves knowledge from several programming languages, compilers, software and hardware environments. Several different technologies grown in the last decades enable developers to write applications

for supercomputers. Most famous for distributed memory clusters is the Message Passing Interface (MPI)[45, 46, 47]. MPI is a standard rather than a own language to enable processes to communicate with each other. It appeared in nineties and is the most famous message-passing library standard for parallel programming today[48]. Writing parallel programs using MPI is regarded as highly difficult. Guo *et al.* implemented a MPI based Fortran 77 version of the Cell Dynamics scheme that shows impressive speedups for large systems e.g. 512^3 [49, 50]. In the last few years, multicore processor systems became famous. Dual- and quad-core systems are available today. These systems can be addressed by using for example the OpenMP Application Programming Interface (API) that became very wide spread for symmetric multiprocessing (SMP) machines[51]. OpenMP makes use of single shared memory, whereas MPI uses distributed (dedicated) memory. It provides a task-level parallelisation for applications, sharing the same memory for the application. *Schreier* studied OpenMP for the Cell Dynamics scheme using C++ in greater detail and achieved interesting results for the speedup of the scheme[52]. Larger systems and supercomputers like the SGI Altix 3700 series include the NUMAflex architecture (Non-Uniform Memory Access) following SMP for many-multicore systems[53].

Recently, researchers and developers found ways to address the massive computational resource given by today's graphics processing units (GPU). In 2007, NVIDIA Corporation introduced CUDA (Compute Unified Device Architecture) to enable developers programming the GPU as a fast co-processors for the CPU[5]. This technology is becoming very popular for various computational physics methods, e.g. Molecular Dynamics[54]. Due to its chip design architecture, the GPU out-performs today's CPUs when it comes to single-precision floating-point calculations. More general standards to form a cross-platform standard for heterogenous computing are in the making, like the proposed OpenCL (Open Computing Language) standard[55]. Using the CUDA API, it is possible to accelerate non-graphics applications. Application development is done in standard C programming language with language extensions (CUDA), but also a Fortran and Python wrapper exist. Once the software is written, it can be executed on the heterogenous environment: parts of the program are executed on CPU (host) and parts of the program, that are highly expensive in computation, are executed on the GPU. Both devices act with separate RAM (DRAM) memory.

In this study, Cell Dynamics scheme is implemented on GPU by NVIDIA CUDA. Two different strategies are introduced for the GPU code and a spatial decomposition from two to one dimension is provided for a reference C implementation. Further, a Fortran 90 reference implementation acts as a benchmarking backbone for the total study. Simulations for different two dimensional system sizes, which are compa-

Figure 3.2: Heterogenous layout of host computer and GPU device. Both devices are connected by a high bandwidth bus with each having its own global RAM (DRAM) memory.

$2 \times 1.19 \times 96 = 229$ GFLOPS is obtained[57]. NVIDIA Quadro GPU cards deliver memory up to 4 GB at the moment. Each MP is made of 8 processors with a size of 16 KB shared memory (parallel data cache)[5, 57]. To reveal further technical details about the installed GPU card and its processor type as well as bandwidth connection (that is the connection between the host machine and the GPU device card as it is shown in Figure 3.2) on a particular computer system, it is recommended to consult the *deviceQuery* and *bandwidthTest* tools provided by the Software Development Kit (SDK) from NVIDIA. The processors perform computation in SIMT fashion (Single-Instruction-Multiple-Thread), which is similar to SIMD (Single-Instruction-Multiple-Data)[56]. Following Flynn's taxonomy of classification of parallel computers, hardware may support single instruction stream or multiple instruction streams manipulating a single data stream or multiple data streams[48]. Here, SIMD refers to a system with single instruction stream and multiple data stream. The GPU, processor arrays and pipelined vector processors belong to this category. It is worth to mention in addition, that modern CPUs are also having a powerful implementation of SIMD instructions, including AMDs 3DNow! and Intels SSE3, SSE4, MMX, etc. technology-features to achieve faster computation[58].

3.3 The CUDA programming environment

GPUs are primarily programmed using graphics APIs and shading languages like OpenGL. NVIDIA introduced CUDA, which is an extension to the the C/C++ programming language and an answer to General Purpose Graphics Processing Unit (GPGPU) programming. In general, the program written is a serial program that is run on the CPU (host) and particular parts of the program are executed on the GPU (device), so that the GPU acts as a co-processors for the CPU. GPU program parts are called *Kernels*,

which may be a function or full program. In other words, a Kernel is called from the host and run on the device as it is shown in Figure 3.3. Only one Kernel is executed at a time, however many threads are executed within each Kernel as a set of parallel threads[56]. Launching a Kernel within a Kernel is not allowed, however once called it is executed N times in parallel by N different CUDA threads[5]. CUDA threads are lightweight and therefore saving a creation overhead. Threads are organized in a hierarchy of *grids* and *thread blocks*. A grid is a collection of thread blocks and a thread block is a set of concurrent threads. Calling a Kernel, the number of threads per block and the number of blocks making up the grid have to be defined initially. In case of Revision 1.0 GPU hardware, 512 threads per block is the maximum allowed configuration set. Threads within each block are able to communicate and share data within each block, however not between different blocks. The change of the configuration settings allows developers to scale code for different GPU architectures, with no source-code modification needed and scalation to different GPU architectures is possible. More precise, each thread is having a unique thread-ID number $threadIdx = 0, 1, 2, \dots (blockDim - 1)$ within its thread block, where $blockDim$ is the dimension of the block, respectively. $threadIdx$ is of type `uint3` that is composed of three integers. Further, each thread block has its own block-ID number, given by $blockIdx$. The block layout is defined by a variable type `dim3 (x, y, z)` to specify the dimensions. If the layout `dim3 (x, y)` is defined, z is automatically set equal to 1. Moreover, each Kernel thread has access to different memory spaces with different scope, size, life-time and latency as it is depicted from the GPU memory chart, Figure 3.4.

Figure 3.3: Heterogenous executing of code on host (CPU) and device (GPU) within time. Each Kernel is getting executed on the device with a specific Kernel configuration that specifies the grid size, block size, etc. including the numerical part to be solved within the Kernel call.

Figure 3.4: GPU memory chart: Threads share local memory and register memory. Thread-blocks share shared-memory that is very fast, however very small in cache size. Different Kernels may access global memory that is uncached and large, however access is very slow.

A Kernel is defined with a `__global__` entry point with no return (that is *void*), for example:

```
__global__
void kernel_example(int x, float* M, ...) { ... }
```

The Kernel invocation from the main CUDA-code has the syntax:

```
kernel_example<<<dimGrid, dimBlock>>>( ... parameter list ... )
```

Where `dimGrid=dim3(x,y)` is the number of blocks being lunched and `dimBlock=dim3(x,y,z)` is the number of threads per block being invoked. There are two more function-qualifiers, namely

`__device__` that declares a function that is executed on the device and can be called from the device only, and `__host__`, that can be called from the host only. As a consequence of the physical separation between GPU and CPU, memory management is needed to address either local or global memory, with both GPU and CPU having their own DRAM (GDDR3) memory. The CUDA API provides functions to allocate and copy data between devices, using `cudaMalloc(...)` and `cudaMemcpy(...)` [59, 5]. As an example, let us consider the following function:

```
cutilSafeCall(
cudaMemcpy(gpu_array, cpu_array, size, cudaMemcpyHostToDevice) );
```

It transfers a host allocated memory array `cpu_array` to a device allocated array `gpu_array`. The function has *kind* `cudaMemcpyHostToDevice`. Parameter `size` is obtained by precalculation and assigning `size_t size = NX*NY*sizeof(float)`, where `NX` and `NY` represent the system lattice size in two dimensions in single-precision floating point precision. Parameter *kind* can be any of the following four: `cudaMemcpyHostToDevice`, `cudaMemcpyDeviceToHost`, `cudaMemcpyHostToHost`, `cudaMemcpyDeviceToDevice`. The function call itself is mapped by a `cutilSafeCall(...)` routine call to ensure proper execution. The headerfile `#include <cutil.h>` has to be included in this case. Within the `cutil.h` library or *CUTIL*, there is an additional support for parsing command line arguments to the main program as well as macros to check errors, timers, etc. which are implemented as `cutilDeviceInit`, `cutilCheckError`, `cutilCreateTimer`, `cutilStartTimer` `cutilStopTimer`. Timers are used within the Cell Dynamics implementation to benchmark time. That allows to measure time in the microseconds for different parts of the program. The total measured time is equal to the wall-clock time (see Linux/Unix command `time`). The call of CUTIL functions will not affect performance. The source files within the `./NVIDIA_CUDA_SDK/common/*` folder and sub directories have to be consulted for more details on CUTIL.

3.4 Implementation of Cell Dynamics using CUDA

The basic idea of the implementation is given by samples provided by the CUDA SDK. The approach is to build two codes: a CUDA (GPU-enabled) version and a second, a C language (CPU-enabled) version, also referred as *Gold*-version. This gives developers the possibility to compare results and validate CUDA code against C version. For Cell Dynamics simulation, the array holding the order parameter ψ

is created and initialized on host and copied to the GPU device. A Kernel routine is then executed and device memory is copied back to the host with a followed de-allocation of all addressed memory. The example below is part of the main program, e.g. `main.cu`:

```
float* pxi_host;
float* pxi_device;
pxi_host = (float*)malloc(size);
pxi_device = cudaMalloc((void **) &pxi_device, size);

cutilSafeCall(
  cudaMemcpy(pxi_device, pxi_host, size, cudaMemcpyHostToDevice) );
kernel_mykernel<<<dimGrid, dimBlock>>>( ...parameter... );
cutilSafeCall(
  cudaMemcpy(pxi_host, pxi_device, size, cudaMemcpyDeviceToHost) );

cudaFree(pxi_device)
free(pxi_host)
cudaThreadExit();
```

The specification of the execution setting (`<<<dimGrid, dimBlock>>>`) for the Kernel is not shown here. The `dimBlock` setting can be product (smaller than 512) of any two values, e.g. for `dim3(16,16)` that is equal to 256 threads. The `dimGrid` setting is derived from the expression $dim3(x,y) = (NX,NY)/(threads.x - 2, threads.y - 2)$ which insures a proper execution that is needed to set the intrinsic block decomposition (data parallelisation) on the GPU. Within the `kernel_mykernel`, data-parallel numerics are implemented to execute in parallel on the GPU.

The *Makefile* looks like this:

```
EXECUTABLE := gpu_main
CUFILES := main.cu
CU_DEPS := kernel_one.cu kernel_two.cu etc.
CCFILES := gold_main.cpp
USEFASTMATH := 1
include ../../common/common.mk
```

Here, the `common.mk` file is the parent Makefile to the programs Makefile and is provided by NVIDIA to ensure that compilation is done properly using libraries, paths, etc. that are needed. The program executable is `gpu_main`. First, Cell Dynamics was implemented in C language as a precursor for the CUDA-version. It also acts as benchmark code against the GPU implementation, alongside the original Fortran 90 implementation of the scheme. The C implementation introduces a new performance enhancement, namely the two-dimensional to one-dimensional domain-decomposition or partitioning. Here, all calculations are done using one-dimensional vector arrays instead of two-dimensional matrices, see Figure 3.5. Compared to the Gold-version, the CUDA implementation is split into the host-part

Figure 3.5: 2D to 1D domain decomposition in the x-y plane. This way, huge amounts of computational resources can be saved and the scheme has a high speedup compared to computation in real two- or three-dimensional space.

and the device-part, which enables Cell Dynamics to harvest the massive GPU computational power for arithmetically intensive parts of the algorithm. The CUDA- and Gold-version run with the same physical-based initialisation (i.e. lamellae diblock morphology), and therefore can be directly compared. The versions run serially one after another to benchmark them individually. The simulation is based on periodic boundary conditions applied on a square (two-dimensional) grid of different sizes. The treatment of the boundaries can be understood from Figure 3.6. In the following, two different CUDA-

Figure 3.6: Formulation of periodic boundary conditions using one-layer halo points as reservoir. Grid edges are exchanged as well as corners are flipped.

based implementation of Cell Dynamics simulation are presented as pseudo-codes. Using four Kernels (4K) one has:

```

Define simulation parameters
Allocate host/device memory arrays
Initialize  $\psi$  with random values for host/device (both same)
Copy host/device memory
  Start time loop (CUDA)
  {
    Call Kernel 1 Laplacian and eq. (2.16),  $\psi^{new} \leftarrow \psi^t$ 
    Call Kernel 2 boundary conditions,  $\psi^{new'} \leftarrow \psi^{new}$ 
  }

```

```

    Call Kernel 3 Laplacian and eq. (2.13),  $\psi^{new''} \leftarrow \psi^{new'}$ 
    Call Kernel 4 boundary conditions,  $\psi^{(t+1)} \leftarrow \psi^{new''}$ 
    Output data every T time steps
}
Stop time loop (CUDA)
Start time loop (Gold)
{
Run Gold version (Cell Dynamics in C language)
Output data every T time steps
}
Stop time loop (Gold)
Free all host/device memory
Output system parameters and timer measurements
(Postprocess visualize and analyze results)

```

In the 4K scheme, four different Kernels with individual algorithmic internals are called and executed on the GPU. Memory copy operations occur before the simulation time loop, after the last time step and while outputting results. Initialization of the order parameter is outside the time loop and for both the CUDA-version and Gold-version have similar values. Output is generated every T time steps. Kernel 1 includes Cell Dynamics equation 2.16 and the first Laplacian, Kernel 2 contains the first update of boundary conditions, Kernel 3 includes Cell Dynamics equation 2.13 and the second Laplacian and Kernel 4 updates boundary conditions again. As a special feature for validation and benchmarking, a so-called Zero-Kernel (K0) was introduced to measure execution time from a blank Kernel call, that is not shown in the pseudo-code representation.

The two Kernel implementation (2K) is slightly different and shown in the following pseudo-code:

```

Define simulation parameters
Allocate host/device arrays
Initialize  $\psi$  with random values for host/device (both same)
Copy host/device memory arrays
    Start time loop (CUDA)
    {

```

```

    Call Kernel 1 Laplacian and eq. (2.16),  $\psi^{new} \leftarrow \psi^t$ 
    Copy device/host memory
    Calculate boundary conditions on host,  $\psi^{new'} \leftarrow \psi^{new}$ 
    Copy host/device memory
    Call Kernel 2 Laplacian and eq. (2.13),  $\psi^{new''} \leftarrow \psi^{new'}$ 
    Copy device/host memory
    Calculate boundary conditions on host,  $\psi^{(t+1)} \leftarrow \psi^{new''}$ 
    Output data every T time steps
    Copy host/device memory
}
Stop time loop (CUDA)
Start time loop (Gold)
{
    Run Gold version (Cell Dynamics in C language)
    Output data every T time steps
}
Stop time loop (Gold)
Free all host/device memory
Output system parameters and timer measurements
(Postprocess visualize and analyze results)

```

The 2K scheme reduced the amount of Kernel calls by factor 2. However, it is needed to introduce host/device or device/host memory copy operations to permit proper boundary condition evaluation.

3.5 Benchmarking results and discussion

The Cell Dynamics simulation method was implemented using a four Kernel and two Kernel approach. It was found that Cell Dynamics scheme can be coded using single-floating point precision. This is a new important insight for future implementations. The scheme was developed on a Linux 2.6, Intel Xeon dual quad-core 3.0 GHz 64-bit machine with 16 GB RAM, 6 MB L2 cache per quad-core. All results are compared both with the existing Fortran 90 reference implementation and C implementation developed within this project. The Fortran 90 code is a three-dimensional version with nested-array

loops. The C version is regarded as the Gold-version and is numerically about 95% similar to the CUDA implementation. With a simulation setup for lamellae diblock copolymer system ($\tau = 0.36$, $f = 0.48$, $u = 0.38$, $v = 2.3$, $B = 0.02$, $D = 0.7$, $A = 1.5$)[1], simulation results presented serve as a benchmark to test technological advances. All simulation runs for the Gold-version were limited to one CPU-core only. The total execution time for both GPU and CPU is in perfect agreement with the system user time measured by the Linux command `time`. All simulations are for two-dimensions with different lattices sizes. For the CUDA implementation, it is found that all measured time scales linear, e.g. simulation for 1000 time steps is comparable with simulation for 10000 time steps, scaled by a factor $\approx 10x$. The Zero-Kernel (K0) execution time is negligible and is only slightly increasing with the systems grid size. It is within the range (0.69... 2.52) *ms* for the measurements. Results of data are shown in Tables 3.1 and 3.2. Figures 3.7, 3.9, 3.8 and 3.10 are based on the CUDA profiling tool `cudaprof`, the CUDA Visual Profiler. The speedup is given by

$$S = \frac{T_{CPU}}{T_{GPU}} \quad (3.1)$$

where T is the measured time for GPU or CPU. From Figure 3.7 one sees that apart from the two Kernel calls, the memory copy operation is the most expensive part of the code. Figure 3.8 shows that the boundary condition update at each time step is the most expensive part of the code due to its non data-parallel implementation. Figure 3.9 shows that at every time step the memory copy operations from host to device and vice versa are consuming large amounts of GPU time and hence overall simulation time. Figure 3.9 confirms that the boundary condition update consumes most of the GPU time due to its non data-parallel implementation. Based on Table 3.1 the speedup for two and four Kernel GPU versions against C version can be plotted as it is shown in Figure 3.11. An efficient speedup can be proposed by employing another boundary update method using auxiliary boundary index arrays. That would allow to eliminate stages in fifths and sevenths columns of Table 3.1. The resulting speedup would be as it is shown in Figure 3.11 by the dotted line, which demonstrate a noticeable improvement. Figure 3.12 demonstrate an impressive speedup for CUDA version compared to Fortran 90 implementation for the box sizes reaching 1024^2 . For the larger boxes, the speedup saturates. That can be attributed to memory limitations.

L^2	Time steps	K0	K1	K2	K3	K4	Total (GPU)	Total (CPU)	\mathcal{S}
$256^2(254^2)$	10	0.69	3.47	9.29	3.29	9.35	26	51	2.0
$512^2(510^2)$	10	0.77	11.60	32.62	11.03	32.10	88	210	2.4
$1024^2(1022^2)$	10	1.10	44.08	134.11	41.87	134.63	356	857	2.4
$2048^2(2046^2)$	10	2.11	195.91	516.09	166.65	517.74	1399	3448	2.5
L^2	Time steps	K0	K1	on host	K3	on host	Total (GPU)	Total (CPU)	\mathcal{S}
$256^2(254^2)$	10	0.73	3.47	4.84	3.54	4.38	17	47	2.8
$512^2(510^2)$	10	0.8	11.79	17.99	12.17	16.91	59	187	3.1
$1024^2(1022^2)$	10	1.72	44.39	55.31	45.10	52.35	199	766	3.8
$2048^2(2046^2)$	10	2.52	223.59	269.11	167.33	261.36	924	3425	3.8

Table 3.1: The execution configuration is for (16,16) (that is equal to 256) threads. Intrinsic block parameters for CUDA version are derived from the expression $dim3(x,y) = (NX, NY)/(threads.x - 2, threads.y - 2)$. Kernels are labeled K0 ... K4. Compiler options are: `nvcc -O3` and `gcc -O3` as given by the `common.mk` Makefile provided by NVIDIA. All time measurements in `ms` with accuracy $\approx \pm 1.00$ `ms` for 10 time steps due to system load. The speedup \mathcal{S} is defined as ratio between one CPU-core and GPU total execution time.

L^2	Time steps	GPU exec. time	F90 exec. time	\mathcal{S}
$256^2(254^2)$	10	17	170	10.0
$512^2(510^2)$	10	59	1392	23.6
$1024^2(1022^2)$	10	199	14040	70.6
$2048^2(2046^2)$	10	924	58496	63.3

Table 3.2: Fortran 90 and GPU speedup chart for 10 time steps and optimized (-O3) Fortran 90 version that was benchmarked on single-core CPU. The GPU version is the two Kernel implementation. Both versions are slightly different in the way of Cell Dynamics implementation, however the final scheme is benchmarked.

Figure 3.7: GPU summary plot for 10 time steps and two Kernel approach.

Figure 3.8: GPU summary plot for 10 time steps and four Kernel approach.

Figure 3.9: GPU timing for two Kernel approach and 10 time steps, which constitute ca. 70 operations (methods).

Figure 3.10: GPU timing for four Kernel approach and for 10 time steps, which constitute ca. 50 operations (methods). Only the initial memory copy operations are show with no data output generated for 10 time steps.

Figure 3.11: Speedup chart for four Kernel and two Kernel implementation and proposed speedup for boundary condition optimised version benchmarked against spatial-decomposed Gold-version (C language) of Cell Dynamics implementation. The graph is related to data from Table 3.1.

Figure 3.12: Speedup chart for two Kernel GPU version against Fortran 90 implementation of Cell Dynamics. The graph is related to data from Table 3.2.

3.6 Conclusions and outlook

GPU computation has become mainstream by now. The GPU as a computational co-processor offers new advantages for developers to build high performance applications to speedup performance of execution. Here, data-parallel and compute intensive functions can be off-loaded to the device and executed in parallel to save CPU resources and speedup system performance.

The Cell Dynamics scheme was written using NVIDIA CUDA. Premature optimisation was avoided to insure a correct implementation of the technique using global memory (RAM memory) with high latency access times. Both the four Kernel and the two Kernel approach show stable results. It is found that the boundary condition update within a Kernel is much slower compared to one being executed on CPU. This is due to the non data-parallel operations inside the boundary update, where the CPU is faster in execution than the GPU. If one would avoid this by execution on the CPU, that would introduce another bottleneck which is the read/write operations from host memory to device memory and vice versa. In fact, the numerics behind Cell Dynamics simulation are already computational very fast but GPU results are promising for future improvements, e.g. addressing shared memory, reduction to one Kernel call, technical optimisations within the scheme itself, etc. Speedups of the scheme using two Kernel calls are about 5 times compared to a CPU C version that is very fast due to its domain decomposition strategy.

It is believed that a factor of 10 in speedup is possible with optimisation of the CUDA implementation compared to the C version. The fact that the C version is so fast in execution on the CPU can be related to the SIMD instructions within the CPU that speedup one dimensional operations (e.g. vector arrays) dramatically. Benchmarking of GPU code against the Fortran 90 reference implementation of Cell Dynamics achieves impressive speedups of factor 70 for 1024^2 grid size. The future optimisation for the GPU version can include removing the boundary condition update within the time loop completely.

3.7 Summary of tasks

The following tasks were performed:

- Existing supercomputer technologies have been reviewed.
- GPU hardware from UCLAN was found as candidate for implementation of Cell Dynamics.
- The new programming framework CUDA from NVIDIA was learned from scratch based on my University education in C and C++ programming languages.
- For comparison, benchmarking and as precursor for CUDA implementation, Cell Dynamics was written in C language with a spatial domain decomposition using one-dimensional arrays only.
- Cell Dynamics scheme was written using CUDA: Two different versions have been written that show different performance results and highlight on features of heterogenous computing (the blend of CPU and GPU).
- Time measurement features have been introduced for all programs in different ways and have been validated.
- For all simulations, ideal compiler settings, helper scripts and a solid simulation workbench was created.
- All programs were benchmarked for different system sizes for lamellae morphology of block copolymer system.

4 STUDY OF ISOTROPIC AND ANISOTROPIC LAPLACIANS FOR CELL DYNAMICS SIMULATION IN TWO DIMENSIONS

Abstract

The isotropic properties of various discretizations in Cell Dynamics were studied. The Laplacian operator was the target of this research. Original Cell Dynamics simulation employs a particular choice of the Laplacian operator. Five different discretized versions of Laplacians have been investigated in detail. A new setup (circular insertion) has been proposed and developed in C programming language for a convenient analysis of isotropic properties. Additional analysis tools have been coded in C, which include scattering intensity calculation (from Fourier-space pictures) and global order parameter evolution analysis. It was found that block copolymer morphology evolution and structure are sensitive to the isotropic quality of the Laplacian.

4.1 Introduction

The Laplacian is the fundamental differential operator, denoted as Δ . It is the sum of all unmixed second partial derivatives or the divergence of the gradient (or Nabla, ∇ operator) and can be written as

$$\nabla \cdot (\nabla \psi) = \text{div grad } \psi = \Delta \psi = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x_i^2} \quad (4.1)$$

for position variables $\psi = \psi(x_1, \dots, x_N)$ in N dimensions of Cartesian coordinate system. In this study, different numerical schemes for two-dimensional Laplacian have been implemented. This is a key numerical element in Cell Dynamics scheme. The Laplacian is discretized on the grid by application of a finite-difference scheme:

$$\Delta = \mathcal{S} + O(h^n) \quad (4.2)$$

where \mathcal{S} represents a stencil matrix (also called mask) and $O(h^n)$ is the truncation error of the order n due to finite mesh size h . The lattice spacing is h (grid resolution). The coordinates x and y in two dimensions are $x_n = nh$ and $y_n = nh$. For a nine-point (9P) Laplacian, the spatial mask of (4.2) is given by

$$\Delta = \frac{1}{h^2} \begin{Bmatrix} \beta & \alpha & \beta \\ \alpha & \gamma & \alpha \\ \beta & \alpha & \beta \end{Bmatrix} + O(h^2) \quad (4.3)$$

Figure 4.1: Shape of Laplacian on 2D grid. Dots indicate $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) = 0$ and black boxes indicate $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) \neq 0$ as declared in equation 4.3

with weighting factors α , β and γ . In Figure 4.1, three Laplacian stencils are visualized, which correspond to the formula 4.3. The following condition should be satisfied:

$$\sum_{k=-1}^{+1} \sum_{l=-1}^{+1} \mathcal{S}_{k,l} = 0 \quad (4.4)$$

from which it follows that $\alpha = 1 - 2\beta$ and $\gamma = 4\beta - 4$ for general stencils and any value of β [60]. Another possible representation is given by $\beta = (1 - \alpha)/2$ and $\gamma = -2(1 + \alpha)$ [61]. A numerical Laplacian in two-dimensions can be computed in two-dimensions as a linear combination:

$$\Delta_9 \psi = \mathcal{S} \psi = \sum_{k=-1}^{+1} \sum_{l=-1}^{+1} \mathcal{S}_{k,l} \psi_{i+k, j+l} \equiv \mathcal{S}_{-1,-1} \psi_{i-1, j-1} + \dots \quad (4.5)$$

or applying equation 4.3 one obtains:

$$\Delta_9 \psi = \alpha \sum_{NN} \psi + \beta \sum_{NNN} \psi - \gamma \psi \quad (4.6)$$

where NN stands for the nearest neighbours and NNN - the next-nearest neighbours, e.g. $\psi_{i+1, j+1}$. A sample finite difference scheme on the grid (that is a 5P stencil with $\alpha = 1/4$, $\beta = 0$ and $\gamma = -1$) can be written like equation [25.3.30] of Ref. [62]:

$$\Delta_5 \psi_{i,j} = \frac{1}{h^2} [\psi_{i+1,j} + \psi_{i-1,j} + \psi_{i,j+1} + \psi_{i,j-1} - 4\psi_{i,j}] + O(h^2) \quad (4.7)$$

In case of Cell Dynamics simulation, Oono und Puri[29, 31, 41] introduced $\alpha = 1/6$, $\beta = 1/12$ and $\gamma = -1$. For a physical problem the obtained patterns, should be as isotropic as possible[32], so the physics is not influenced by the discretization on the grid. That can result in a rather unconventional form of the stencil in equation (4.3)[32]. For the nonconserved order parameter in the Cell Dynamics scheme (see Ref. [29]), anisotropy is not effected by different Laplacians introduced. However, for the conserved (see Ref. [29]), pattern formation is influenced by different Laplacians, especially at later stages of the system evolution. Inclusion of next-nearest-neighbor cells are not necessary for the nonconserved-order-parameter case, but it is crucial in the conserved-order-parameter case[29]. To study this issue in more

detail, one can use Fourier space representation. In Fourier space, the Laplacian is given by:

$$\nabla^2 = -\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{k} \quad (4.8)$$

where \mathbf{k} is the wave-vector in Fourier series expansion. The 5P sample stencil given by equation (4.7) it follows[32, 63],

$$\mathcal{F}(\Delta_5) = 2\alpha[\cos k_x + \cos k_y - 2] \quad (4.9)$$

with $h = \Delta x = \Delta y = 1$. Taylor expansion in Fourier-space is a tool to study the quality of the discretization. It was found that the truncation error increases from left to right[32]:

$$O(\Delta_{9P,star}) < O(\Delta_{9P}) < O(\Delta_{5P,tri}) < O(\Delta_{5P}). \quad (4.10)$$

The 9P-star stencil is given by equation [25.3.31] of Ref. [62] and is outside of the scope of our study. Similary, the 5P triangular-lattice stencil is not studied due to different grid symmetry which is not compatible with periodic boundary conditions.

It should be noted that Fourier transform measure is also used to study experimental data as it is related to the scattering intensity in physical experiments. The intensity is proportional to the structure factor, which can be written as[15]:

$$S_{\mathbf{k}} = |\psi_{\mathbf{k}}|^2 = \psi_{\mathbf{k}}\psi_{\mathbf{k}}^* \quad (4.11)$$

Integration over the angle gives $S(k)$.

Space-based $\psi_{\mathbf{r}}$ values are transformed to wave vector-based $\psi_{\mathbf{k}}$ values. For a system size of 256^2 , Fast Fourier Transformation (FFT) is preferred (power of 2) over the Discrete Fourier Transformation (DFT) as it reduces the number of computations needed for N points from $O(N^2)$ to $O(N \log_2 N)$ [64]. Generally speaking, the two-dimensional DFT is given by[64],

$$\mathcal{F}(\psi_{m,n}) = \sum_{k_2=0}^{L_2-1} \sum_{k_1=0}^{L_1-1} \exp\left(\frac{-i2\pi k_2 n}{L_2}\right) \exp\left(\frac{-i2\pi k_1 m}{L_1}\right) \psi_{k_1,k_2} \quad (4.12)$$

and can be rewritten as[65],

$$\mathcal{F}(\psi_{m,n}) = \sum_{k_2=0}^{L_2-1} \sum_{k_1=0}^{L_1-1} W^{mL_1 k_2 + nL_2 k_1} \psi_{k_1,k_2} \quad (4.13)$$

where $W = \exp(-i2\pi/L_1 L_2)$ [65]. To calculate FFT in two dimensions one can sequentially apply two FFT's in one dimension[64]:

$$\mathcal{F}^{FFT_{2D}}(\psi_{m,n}) = FFT_{Index1}(FFT_{Index2}[\psi_{k_1,k_2}]) \quad (4.14)$$

Figure 4.2: Random initial values (by Mersenne Twister random number generator) starting configuration with artificial spot in middle to validate isotropic and anisotropic Laplacians visually. Random numbers are $\psi = -0.3$, $\psi = 0.3$ and $\psi = 0.6$. The grid size is 256^2

4.2 Implementation of Laplacians

The Cell Dynamics technique was implemented in C programming language. Despite the fact that the scheme is computationally very fast compared to other simulation methods, the scheme was optimized and re-written with 2D-to-1D decomposition (as can be seen in Figure 3.5). Simulation results with different Laplacian masks are presented in Table 4.3. Grid spacing is $h = \Delta x = \Delta y = 1$ and the maximum simulation time is 10000. The time step size is 100. The two-dimensional grid size is 256^2 . Memory allocation is realised in a dynamic fashion. Boundary conditions are periodic as shown in Figure 3.6. All values are in good agreement for simulation of lamellae structure, since it is found that the morphology does not change significantly after a certain time, which is in agreement with earlier simulations[30]. The computing environment for simulation was Linux 2.6 with Intel P4 HT 3.2 GHz CPU (32-bit, 2 MB L2 cache), 4 GB RAM, GNU gcc compiler 4.3 with optimisation option -O3 and all simulation runs are restricted to one CPU-core.

An additional C program was written to generate a pseudo-random number sequence for the ordering parameter ψ . The *Mersenne Twister (MT19937)* algorithm by Makoto Matsumoto and Takuji Nishimura with a period of $2^{19937} - 1$ [66] was used with an initial seed. As suggested by Sevink, a artificial

Figure 4.3: Zoom of artificial circle of fixed values within square of random numbers: A digital circle is not perfect, therefore fine step size in generation is needed to reproduce the full shape. The spot is related to Figure 4.2 that shows the full picture of the initial starting configuration.

spot (i.e. filled circle) was introduced in the initial configuration to study isotropy effects[67]. For that purpose a specific program was written to implement the circle-algorithm, which is based on the geometrical definitions of a circle using sine and cosine functions with a very fine step width of less than 0.1. A variant of the Bresenham-algorithm[68] can also be used here and was implemented in early development phase of this program, however was abandoned later in favour of a more simple circle algorithm. As it can be seen from Figure 4.3, a circle on a grid is never perfect and smoothing was implemented. Different configurations can be created, for instance Figure (4.2) shows a circle where higher values are inside whereas the surrounding is random. The Cell Dynamics scheme is free to evolve from the starting configuration. The global order parameter should satisfy the conservation condition:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int d\mathbf{r} \psi = 0 \quad (4.15)$$

An additional programming tool was developed within the project to analyse condition (4.15) during the simulation run.

4.3 Results and discussion

Table 4.3 presents results for various Laplacian masks. It was found that masks A, B and D are stable in a similar range of parameters A and D , whereas mask C was always unstable in that range. A characteristic image of unstable pattern evolution is presented in Figure 4.4. Mask A was found to yield the fastest algorithm. Both isotropic Laplacians D and E result in approximately the same fast algorithms. A detailed performance analysis for masks A, B, D and E is shown in Figures 4.5, 4.6, 4.7 and 4.8.

Images a) show a sequence of snapshots of Cell Dynamics runs. Images b) show Fourier transform of initial stages of systems evolution. In Figure 4.5 c), the condition (4.15) is presented as function of time. One sees that the condition is fulfilled only after approximately 400 time steps. This can be explained by the fact that the initial circle serves as perturbation to the system. The same check of the conditions was performed for other Laplacian stencil masks and gave similar results, which can be explained by the same initial circle configuration for all stencils.

The circular shape allows to observe easily non-isotropic results from the mask A, which can be seen as "square" lamellae circle in the centre of the Figure 4.5 a) bottom. It can be also observed that many lamellae are parallel to the grid lines. The Fourier transform shows a characteristic cross pattern, which is another non-isotropic feature. One also observes that the phase separation is rather slow, which is seen both in a slow change in scattering intensities in Figures 4.5 d) and e) and relatively short and deformed lamellae in Figure 4.5 a) bottom. Similar situation is observed for masks B, Figure 4.6. The Fourier transform has a cross pattern which does not relax with time, Figures 4.5 b) and e). The rotation of the cross pattern with respect to Figure 4.5 b) is due to the choice of next neighbours in the stencil (compare first two stencil in Figure 4.1). Non-isotropy is also evident from deformed circular lamellae in Figure 4.6 a). The phase separation is relatively slow as well, which is seen in short lamellae and relatively broad scattering peak of the final structure, Figure 4.6 d) (black line). The scheme shows elements of instability which manifests itself in non-monotonic behaviour of scattering peaks in Figure 4.6 c) (oscillation in height) and in non-physical gray regions in Figure 4.6. Both masks D and E show perfect isotropic behaviour which can be seen from visual inspection of Figures 4.7 a) and 4.8 a) and from the circular shape of Fourier transform b) and e). The phase separation is relatively fast which is reflected in substantial increase in the scattering peak heights, Figures 4.7 and 4.8 c) and d). However, the structures are not identical. The shape of the scattering peaks d) (e.g. black curve) are somewhat different, which corresponds to different structures in Figures 4.7 and 4.8, a). While the final morphology in a) bottom is purely lamellae. The morphology in Figure 4.8 a) bottom is a coexistence of lamellae and spherical

Mask	α	β	γ	Ref.	Stencil	A (stable)	D (stable)	Exec. time (s)	Time steps
A	1/4	0	-1	[29, 69, 62]	Aniso.	1.3	0.4 (< 0.5)	≈ 28	10000
B	0	1/4	-1	[63]	Aniso.	1.3	0.4	≈ 32	10000
C	1/30	1/120	-1	[69, 62]	Aniso.	–	–	–	10000
D	1/6	1/12	-1	[29, 41, 61]	Iso.	1.5	0.7	≈ 40	10000
E	2/10	1/20	-1	[60]	Iso.	1.5	0.7	≈ 41	10000

Table 4.1: Table of different stencil masks (A-F). Aniso.: anisotropic; Iso.: isotropic; Ref.: Reference; Exec. time: Executable run time; All time measurements are within ± 1 s of accuracy due to system load etc. All simulations were performed for lamellae copolymer morphology using $\tau = 0.36$, $f = 0.48$, $u = 0.38$, $v = 2.3$, $B = 0.02$, $D = 0.7$, $A = 1.5[1]$.

Figure 4.4: Results of CDS after 100 time steps for Laplacian stencil C from Table 4.3. The scheme is found to be unstable.

phase. Therefore the discretization can influence both kinetics and the final structure.

Figure 4.5: CDS results for stencil A (Table 4.3). a) Real space simulation snapshots with an artificial circle in the centre for 100, 200, 1000 and 10000 time steps. b) FFT of the snapshot at 100 time steps. c) Global order parameter evolution. d), e) Time evolution of the scattering intensity.

Figure 4.6: CDS results for stencil B (Table 4.3). a) Real space simulation snapshots with an artificial circle in the centre for 100, 200, 1000 and 10000 time steps. b) FFT of the snapshot at 100 time steps. c), d) Time evolution of the scattering intensity. e) FFT of the snapshot at 10000 time steps.

Figure 4.7: CDS results for stencil D (Table 4.3). a) Real space simulation snapshots with an artificial circle in the centre for 100, 200, 1000 and 10000 time steps. b) FFT of the snapshot at 100 time steps. c), d) Time evolution of the scattering intensity. e) FFT of the snapshot at 10000 time steps.

Figure 4.8: CDS results for stencil E (Table 4.3). a) Real space simulation snapshots with an artificial circle in the centre for 100, 200, 1000 and 10000 time steps. b) FFT of the snapshot at 100 time steps. c), d) Time evolution of the scattering intensity. e) FFT of the snapshot at 10000 time steps.

4.4 Conclusions and outlook

Several different Laplacians for the Cell Dynamics scheme were studied. All simulation was conducted for a diblock lamellae copolymer system using the parameters $\tau = 0.36$, $f = 0.48$, $u = 0.38$, $v = 2.3$, $B = 0.02$, $D = 0.7$, $A = 1.5$ [1]. In real space, depending on the scheme parameters A and D and the selected stencil, either stable or non-stable solutions are found. The stencil plays an important role for the quality of the evolution of the order parameter. The selection by Oono and Puri can be confirmed as a good choice. Another stencil shows similar results, however both systems take much longer to equilibrate and form structures compared to stencils that are less isotropic. Fourier space images presented give an idea for the experimental found structures, where it was found that the stencil has huge influence on the scattering picture and evolution of structure factor. Using an artificial shape in the centre of our diblock lamellae copolymer system allows for a detailed analysis of the isotropicity of results. New visualisation tools were programmed for the Cell Dynamics scheme. The performance is mildly influenced by the different stencils due to the fact that not many multiplication and addition operations are introduced per stencil, however it is suggested that the choice of a stencil can influence the speed by $\approx 30\%$ if larger than 5P and 9P stencils are included in the scheme. Both kinetics and structure are found to be sensitive to the choice of the stencils. Developed additional analysis tools are valuable for the future research of new Laplacian stencils for Cell Dynamics simulation.

4.5 Summary of tasks

The following tasks were performed:

- Laplacian stencil discretization for Cell Dynamics technique was reviewed.
- The mathematical aspects of stencils were studied and mapped to the scheme.
- A particular C program was written to generate random numbers using a Mersenne Twister generator library.
- Another C program was written to insert an artificial shape of values for the initial configuration to study isotropicity.
- Cell Dynamics was written in C programming language with a spatial domain decomposition using one-dimensional arrays only, that is very fast in execution and is used throughout this study.
- Application of Fourier analysis to study Laplacian isotropic properties was learnt.

- For all simulations, ideal compiler settings, helper scripts and a solid simulation workbench have been employed.
- Different Laplacians applied to the Cell Dynamics scheme have been studied for isotropicity. Results are presented in real space and Fourier space as well as scattering peaks of evolution are presented for lamellae diblock copolymer system with 256^2 grid size.

5 OUTLOOK OF FUTURE WORK: CELL DYNAMICS WITH CRANK-NICHOLSON SCHEME

Abstract

For the future work of modelling block copolymers, suggestions have been made regarding employment of different discretization schemes such as Crank-Nicholson. A small part of research is given here about the implementation of Crank-Nicholson method with a proposed solution method (Conjugate Gradient method).

5.1 Crank-Nicholson implementation research

Proposed by Crank and Nicholson[70], the Crank-Nicholson (CN) technique is a candidate to solve partial differential equations numerically using a finite difference (FD) approach. A second-order accuracy in time and space $O(h^2, \Delta t^2)$ is obtained and the method is regarded numerically stable, however oscillations can still occur. It is an implicit method and widely used FD method for the modelling of heat-diffusive problems in one or more dimension. The scheme is made up with a half explicit step and half implicit step, each with time step $\Delta t/2$. An averaging at the i th and $(i + 1)$ th time step is given for the spatial difference. In other words, it is the average of the forward Euler and backward Euler method with a central difference in space.

The study here is an overview of steps needed to solve the Time-Dependent Ginzburg-Landau (TDGL) equation based on CN technique.

The following fundamental partial differential equation (PDE) is of particular interest for the simulation of copolymers due to its diffusive nature. Modelling at the mesoscale level with a density field description and free energy formulation is introduced. The PDE is given as:

$$\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = \nabla^2 \psi - \nabla^2 (\mathcal{F}(\psi) + D \nabla^2 \psi) \quad (5.1)$$

with ψ the spatial order parameter, t the time, ∇^2 the Laplacian, $\mathcal{F}(\psi)$ the free energy functional and D , a diffusion parameter. The equation is non-linear and fourth-order, including the Bi-Laplacian or Biharmonic operator ∇^4 .

The CN method is convenient in particular for one or two dimensions, however for two or more dimensions, the Alternating Direction Implicit method (ADI) is favoured due to the simpler equations that

need to be solved and hence, faster results are obtained. In two dimensions, the ADI method splits the FD equation into two implicit equations that result in a system of symmetric and tridiagonal equations suitable for e.g. Cholesky decomposition or LU decomposition.

The solution of the PDE is related to a solution of a $\mathbf{A}x = b$ system, that is $x = \mathbf{A}^{-1}b$ where x is an unknown vector, b is a known vector and \mathbf{A} is a known, symmetric and positive-definite matrix. For a grid size of 100 in two dimensions, 10000 equations need to be solved! Due to the fact that the discretization of the PDE results in a very sparse but huge matrix, iterative methods (or nonstationary methods) like the Conjugate Gradient method (CG) are key to finding fast solutions. CG out-performs Jacobi, Gauss-Seidel and Successive Over Relaxation (SOR) for large systems. Good results can be obtained in \sqrt{N} steps of iteration[71]. The lemma in case of CG is that $\mathbf{A}x = b$ is equivalent to a quadratic minimization problem of the form,

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{2}x^T \mathbf{A}x - x^T b \quad (5.2)$$

with $f \in R^n$. The minimum is reached when $x = A^{-1}b$. The method is effective for symmetric positive systems. It generates vector sequences (i.e. successive approximations to the solution) of conjugates (or orthogals), residuals corresponding to the iterates and search directions used in updating the iterates and residuals[72]. Memory usage is low with this method since only a few number of vectors are required. From the iterates, the residual vectors are also the gradients of a quadratic functional, the minimization of which is equivalent to solving the linear system[72]. Per iteration, on matrix-vector product, three vector updates and two inner products are solved[72]. The basic algorithm for a non-preconditioned CG technique works as following: Given a linear system $\mathbf{A}x = b$, the first step with guess $x^0 = (0, 0, 0)^T$ and $P = P^{-1} = I$, where I is the identity or unit matrix and P the preconditioning matrix, the following CG-algorithm[71]:

Step 0 - Preliminaries

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{A} &\rightarrow a_{i,j}, 1 \leq i, j \leq N \\ b &\rightarrow b_j, 1 \leq j \leq N \\ \mathbf{P} &\rightarrow \gamma_{i,j}, 1 \leq i, j \leq N \\ x &\rightarrow x_i, 1 \leq i \leq N \end{aligned} \quad (5.3)$$

Step 1 - Setup step

$$r^0 = b - \mathbf{A}x^0 \quad (= b)$$

$$w = \mathbf{P}^{-1}r^0 \quad (= b)$$

$$v^1 = \mathbf{P}^{-t}w \quad (= b) \tag{5.4}$$

$$\alpha = \langle w, w \rangle \quad (= \sum_{j=1}^N w_j^2)$$

Step 2 - Start iteration with $k=1$ until $k \leq N$

Step 3 - Check if $v < \textit{Tolerance}$? : Solution x_n , residual r_n found. Stop.

$$u = \mathbf{A}v^1$$

$$t_1 = \frac{\alpha}{\langle v^1, u \rangle} \quad (t_k = \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{\alpha}{v_j u_j})$$

$$x^1 = x^0 + t_1 v^1$$

$$\tag{5.5}$$

$$r^1 = r^0 - t_1 u$$

$$w = \mathbf{P}^{-1}r^1 (= r^1)$$

$$\beta = \langle w, w \rangle \quad (\beta = \sum_{j=1}^N w_j^2)$$

Step 4 - Check if $|\beta| < \textit{Tolerance}$? : If $\|r\| < \textit{Tolerance}$? : Solution x_n , residual r_n found. Stop.

$$s_1 = \frac{\beta}{\alpha}$$

$$v^2 = \mathbf{P}^{-t}w + s_1 v^1 \tag{5.6}$$

$$\alpha = \beta$$

Step 5 - Check if $(k > N)$? : Maximal numbers of iterations exceeded. Stop.

Step 6 - Restart iteration with $k=2$, etc.

$$u = \mathbf{A}v^2$$

$$\dots = \dots$$

$$v^3 = \dots$$

$$\tag{5.7}$$

$$\alpha = \beta$$

The preconditioning matrix $\mathbf{P} \approx \mathbf{L}$, where \mathbf{L} comes from the Cholesky factorization $\mathbf{L}\mathbf{L}^T$ of \mathbf{A} . It follows that $\mathbf{P}^{-1}\mathbf{P}^T \approx \mathbf{A}^{-1}$ is a good approximation[71]. To solve the PDE on a given grid, the discretization

of equation (5.1) depends on its spatial coordinate system. In two dimensions, discrete derivatives are given by Ref. [73] or Ref. [62]:

$$\delta_x \psi_{i,j} = \frac{\psi_{i+1,j} - \psi_{i-1,j}}{2h} \quad (5.8)$$

$$\delta_y \psi_{i,j} = \frac{\psi_{i,j+1} - \psi_{i,j-1}}{2h} \quad (5.9)$$

$$\delta_x^2 \psi_{i,j} = \frac{\psi_{i+1,j} - 2\psi_{i,j} + \psi_{i-1,j}}{h^2} \quad (5.10)$$

$$\delta_y^2 \psi_{i,j} = \frac{\psi_{i,j+1} - 2\psi_{i,j} + \psi_{i,j-1}}{h^2} \quad (5.11)$$

$$i\delta_x^4 \psi_{i,j} = \frac{12}{h^2} ((\delta_x \psi_x)_{i,j} - (\delta_x^2 \psi_x)_{i,j}) \quad (5.12)$$

$$\delta_y^4 \psi_{i,j} = \frac{12}{h^2} ((\delta_y \psi_y)_{i,j} - (\delta_y^2 \psi_y)_{i,j}) \quad (5.13)$$

These equations form the starting point for a new discretization scheme of Cell Dynamics simulation.

5.2 Summary of tasks

The following tasks were performed:

- The fundamental partial differential equation that Cell Dynamics is based on was studied.
- Crank-Nicholson method was investigated for deployment.
- It was found that Conjugate Gradient method is suitable as linear equation solver.
- A basic Conjugate Gradient iterative algorithm is presented.

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